
BOOK REVIEW: THE REDISCOVERY OF INDIA BY MEGHNAD DESAI

BY SAKKCHAM SINGH PARMAAR¹

I. INTRODUCTION TO THE BOOK

Meghnad Desai explores the mind of one of the world's most mysterious nations in "The Rediscovery of India." He presents readers with an interesting examination—including this country's difficult past life, hard-to-understand culture, and politics that seem to be without a goal, forces that are mixing contemporary India and showing its position in the whole world, with precision.

Beginning from ancient civilization to modern democracy, this book covers economics, politics, religion, and society in India. In some thoughtful essays, Desai explores the question of diversity, secularism, and social justice that troubles Indian identity as a nation.

In essence, the central policy message of "The Rediscovery of India" is that despite its diversity, India is a strong nation but also recognized for its challenges and contradictions. However, in dealing with such intricacies, Desai employs intricate strategies to help his readers understand well enough what has influenced India's history and what is likely to determine its future and subsequent outlook.

Desai's expertise in economics and political commentary are evident in his enlightening discussions about major issues like globalization, caste system, gender inequality, democracy, etc, all aspects that converge into forming India's fate. Using captivating language and penetrating insights, he forces people to accept present-day facts and contribute towards forming an all-embracing fair society.

Meghnad Desai's "The Rediscovery of India" encourages us to journey through our minds, reflecting on India's history and investigating its present issues to see a future that respects its wealth in tradition and cultural diversity. As India is on the verge of another period of development and change, this book reminds us just when we need it most that Indians are still

¹ Author is a student of O.P. Jindal Global University

as energetic and tough in mind as they have always been before they became famous for all those things they evolved enormously in.

II. MY REVIEW OF THE BOOK

I was fascinated by Meghnad Desai's profound views about India's complicated history, culture, and politics in the book titled "The Rediscovery of India". Desai's meticulous examination made me understand better how complex India is.

The author has an original and interesting way of interrogating facts by posing counterfactual arguments. The writer looks at India's multi-dimensional identity as per my understanding and this led to my deep engagement with the book's topics from how economics influences its way forward to the different societies that are found within it. I was made to think about things by Desai such as a person's position in society in terms of caste; more than one religion that co-exists peacefully on the same land; or even trying to understand why there may be injustice despite so many efforts against it, that is why after reading Desai's book, I had to reconsider some important ideas that I previously had.

I resonated with a lot of Desai's arguments, especially what he had to say about how India is intrinsically a very tough place but also a place that accepts everybody most times, I accept the times when his arguments seemed troubling to me. Still, they served as eye-openers in my life making me realize how complex India can get though I have been here since birth and developing a more meaningful sense of history since people often ask where this country lies in terms of its future.

Personally, Rediscovery of India reminded me of my experiences with Indian culture and history, highlighting how much Desai's work has influenced my thinking and perception. I was able to visualize a future for India when reading the book such that I respect its history while coping with modernization.

At last, "The Rediscovery of India" is more than an excellent intellectual tour but more importantly, a clear call to recall, if one wishes to study the country's past objectively and then survive its current period humanly, he should be able to think about it again relating to the values that characterize the Indian spirit and strength through variety as well as development.

III. CONTRASTING OPINION

In numerous significant aspects, Gurcharan Das presents a distinct perspective from that of Meghnad Desai. While Desai's main argument focuses on the intricacies and difficulties that define India, Das, in his book "India Unbound," views this country from an optimistic outlook towards its future especially when it comes to economic growth and globalization.

Das has suggested that India plunged into entrepreneurship and gained global popularity thanks to embracing market reforms and globalization as the emerging economic giant. He praises India for moving from a closed socialist state to an exuberant market-oriented country revealing how liberalization brought opportunities for economic growth and social movement.

Despite Desai's focus on continually existing social inequalities as well as issues like caste-based discrimination, Das has a different view of the country's economic revolution this is seen as a factor that has seen an increase in social mobility as millions escape poverty while simultaneously being able to pursue their desires. He says India has been able to manage globalization therefore accomplishing economic development while at the same time keeping its cultural values and national legacy.

It is the case that Desai and Das possess different viewpoints as a result of their different backgrounds of learning and different beliefs. Desai always sees systemic challenges and structural inequalities in everything because he is always an economist and also a political commentator. On the other hand, his fellow economist Mr. Das brings out a pro-business perspective when it comes to interest rates thus pointing out that inflation may go up or down depending on other factors such as oil prices or government expenditure.

When you compare "The Rediscovery of India" with "India Unbound", it is possible for you to understand how India's developmental process is full of many complex issues and arguments from the perspectives of two different authors who are also held in high regard.

WORKS CITED

Desai, Meghnad. *The Rediscovery of India*. London: Penguin Books, 2009.

Das, Gurcharan. *India Unbound: From Independence to the Global Information Age*. New York: Anchor Books, 2001.